

The three maxims of synthesised ethnography

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1. Whenever possible, use open models. If not possible, appropriate the capabilities of the proprietary model by training your model with it.

- Fine-tuned open models match or exceed GPT-4¹
- LoRA and RAG enable corpus-grounded, domain-adapted analysis²
- Distillation via synthetic data legitimately transfers proprietary capabilities³
- Smaller models sometimes outperform their teacher model⁴
- Proprietary models in research require explicit justification⁵

2. Whenever possible, use your own, sustainable infrastructure.

- Local hosting preserves data, technological, and infrastructural sovereignty⁶
- Proprietary tools routinely fail data sovereignty obligations⁷
- Inference is now AI's dominant lifecycle environmental cost⁸
- Quantisation and local inference cut emissions ~45%⁹
- Institutional computing complements rather than duplicates national infrastructure¹⁰

3. Never, ever, compromise the privacy of your research partners by uploading your data to a "free-to-use" LLM API.

- "Free-to-use" means paid for in data alienation: by default, AI companies train on what users type^{11 12}
- Commercial APIs transfer participant data to external servers¹³
- There is no reliable way to make models forget¹⁴
- Research data extraction continues colonial histories of dispossession¹⁵

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